

Identification of critical metals and potential bottlenecks in passenger cars through a thermodynamic approach

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Abstract:

The automobile sector is one of the main industries to hold the economy of several countries globally since millions of units are manufactured every year. This sector is introducing new technology in every new model being released to obtain more innovative vehicles, conditioned for the Internet of Things (IoT), well established in the current society. Smarter cars carry out a hidden cost that is not being evaluated, the so-called scarcity of mineral resources. In this paper, several car parts of different models will be analyzed with a thermodynamic rarity approach, and a general overview and comparison will be made with the models studied. As a result of the study, it will be obtained to identify the most critical parts of each model, spotting why they are considered at risk with a future bottleneck. Accordingly, some solutions will be provided to avoid the scarcity of some metals and, therefore, avoid breaking the supply chain.

Keywords:

Critical raw material; Recycling; Vehicles; Material bottleneck; Automobile sector

1. Introduction

Society is being driven through neutral emissions by 2050, which was agreed in the Paris agreement [1] by different countries. European Union (EU) is also committed to becoming the first climate-neutral continent in 2050 [2]. However, this could not be under the EU control since factors do not depend on the EU, such as demand for energy, technological breakthroughs, and population growth, among others [3]. Transport represents around 25% of the total emissions [3]. Thus, the improvement in the efficiency of this sector would reduce the greenhouse gas (GHG) sent to the atmosphere since the rate of growth is faster than other sectors [4]. Another way to decrease the emissions relies on decreasing the acquisition of particular vehicles and fostering public transport, car sharing, or other new alternatives like electric bikes [5]. Some countries have already set up a plan to ban diesel vehicles in 2025 and gasoline in 2030 [6], forcing them to carry out to transform the automobile sector.

Following this line, the transport sector is moving forward to new technologies with less CO₂ emissions [7]. An example of this can be the implementation of hydrogen buses in public transport in several cities [8], [9], or implementing changes to reduce the use of vehicles with high emissions like trucks [7]. In regards to society, internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEV) are being substituted for hybrid and battery electric cars (BEV) due to emissions sent to the environment [10]. At the end of 2020, ten million electric cars were on the road, being sold around three million in the same year, corresponding a 4.6% of the total sales [11]. According to the literature review, it is expected to have around 150 million electric cars¹ in 2030, with an average growth of 30% per year, being the 7% of the total fleet in the same year [11]. Moreover, optimistic studies predict that the light-duty sales for electric vehicles in 2050 would be close to 50% in a conservative scenario, representing almost 30% of the global fleet [12]. However, as it is possible to see in Figure 1, there is no common agreement with this sector, since some authors believe that for the year 2050, gasoline vehicles will remain dominant with more than 75% of the sales, counting hybrid and battery electric vehicles BEV only with 15% of the sales share [13].

¹ BEV, ICEV etc.

Figure 1. Light-duty vehicle sales [millions of vehicles] [13]

New car models are designed with more applications in order to ease car driving, as well as the comfort of the vehicle [14], [15]. This development is based on several metals due to the different physical and chemical properties they dispose of. This affirmation can be applied, but it gets more strength with electric vehicles since more metals are manufactured, being some of them critical from the point of view of the supply chain [16], [17]. Some metals, like rare earth elements (REEs), contained in electric engines, or cobalt, which is used in batteries, can be an example of why BEV requires more metals than a traditional car. Although the technology applied for both vehicles (ICEV and BEV) is different, they have common components and car parts that can be manufactured in both of them, such as the infotainment or combi-instrument, among others [18]. However, the supply chain risk is not derived from the critical metals inside the vehicle, which is often low, but from the number of vehicles sold every year worldwide [19].

In 2018, more than 98 million motor vehicles were produced (79.3 were passenger cars) [20], which means that tons of metals were needed to supply the automobile industry with the demand. Some metals are expected to reach peak production in the following years (see REE [20]). Thus, regarding the data recycled and introduced in the industry again [22], it would be needed to increase the market share from recycling to satisfy the demand in the automobile sector if the supply chain must be accomplished.

The EU 2000/53/E.C. directive introduced requirements to increase the recycling ratio for the end-of-life vehicles, being established in 95% [21]. Nevertheless, these requirements do not make a difference between abundant and critical metals, but they are only based on mass [21]. This could be accepted if every metal contained the same scarcity on the Earth's crust and the recycling rate was the same for any of them. These conditions are not happening, and therefore, laws and regulations provide the same importance to very different metals, such as iron and cobalt, when they are manufactured and recycled in different ways. At the same time, the energy applied to beneficiate them is very different [22].

Since all metals involved in cars are considered in the same way and under the same circumstances, thermodynamics will be applied in order to identify which is the most critical metal in cars and which components are the most unsustainable from the thermodynamics point of view. Other authors [23], [24] analyzed the risk of the supply chain from an economic perspective and socioeconomic factors, taking into account all factors involved in the production chain. The study of this paper is not only based on the weight of each model and its components but also a physical value by means of thermodynamics. With this approximation, it is possible to provide different importance to each metal based on their scarcity and availability and not in the amount of them manufactured in each vehicle.

2. Methodology and models analyzed

2.1. Methodology

Several studies are analyzing the end-of-life for a vehicle, being carried out through a mass-based assessment [25], [26]. As demonstrated by some authors [27], mass-based assessment of metal content in a vehicle does not incentivize the recovery of minor but extremely valuable elements, such as rare earth elements (REE), precious metals and other essential raw materials required to manufacture electric and electronic equipment. However, as it was aforementioned, this indicator only quantitatively represents the metals, making no difference between scarce and abundant metals. For that reason, it has been considered for this study to apply

another indicator called thermodynamic rarity, which provides a physical value to metals. Exergy is a thermodynamic property that accounts not only for the quantity but also for the quality of any resource. The analysis is based on an exergy-based indicator called thermodynamic rarity [28], and it is possible to assess the mineral resources and provide an energy number to each mineral found in the crust [29]. Therefore, it allows us to evaluate which specific car parts contain the most valuable metals from a physical point of view. This is based on the recognition that the physical value of minerals is mainly due to their chemical properties and their availability on the Earth's crust. Therefore, the scarcer a resource, the greater its extraction costs. The aim of this indicator called thermodynamic rarity (or simply rarity), is to allocate a physical value to raw materials according to the following parameters: (1) their scarcity in nature and (2) the net energy required to extract and refine them to obtain the commodity. Scarce and difficult to obtain commodities such as cobalt are several orders of magnitude have a greater rarity than common ones such as iron. This is due to the embodied energy, which is represented in Figure 2. It is possible to see how the energy increases exponentially when the concentration in mines is being reduced to very low ore grades.

On the other hand, the exergy replacement cost (ERC) can be seen as a bonus provided by Mother Nature since it is being included an avoided cost for having the minerals concentrated and being dispersed at the end of their lives [30]. Thus, Thermodynamic rarity is composed by the embodied energy and the ERC. Moreover, thermodynamic rarity has the advantage of mass- and economic-based approaches. The mass approach is an indicator strictly based on physical aspects of the commodity and hence is universal, objective, and more stable than monetary approaches. Moreover, although alien to the volatility of the commodity markets, with frequent ups and downs of prices, it is also closer to societal perception of value. In this sense, it shares the advantage of the economic approach [31].

Figure 2. Embodied energy when the ore grade decreases [28].

These values have been already calculated [28], being updated later for other authors [32], [33]. This indicator provides another point of view that is possible to apply when metals are involved, being able to identify which are the most critical and which could be at risk of scarcity in the future. This methodology has already been applied in several studies [19], [27], [34], [35], being approved as an indicator of sustainability. It is based on the scarcity of the metals, being calculated these values following the criteria of a total dispersed state, called Thanatia. Thus, this hypothetical reference state is applied as a baseline for evaluating the exergy of any mineral in the crust and opens door to discuss the thermodynamic rarity concept as a basis for exergy analyses for mineral systems [29].

It is important to state that thermodynamic rarity does not take into account how materials are found in a specific vehicle component. Indeed, materials can be homogeneously spread throughout the vehicle, combined with other materials/elements into chemical compounds, or found almost pure in specific components. This fact would obviously very much affect the recyclability of the vehicle [36], but the rarity would remain the same. Thus, a rarity only measures in energy terms the impact of using those raw materials in a vehicle or any other application, considering the state of mineral ores in the Earth and mining and beneficiation energies. It is the first step to identifying car parts containing valuable metals. However, whether such metals can be practically recovered can only be analyzed through a proper recyclability assessment.

This paper aims to analyze the sustainability of different car parts, make an assessment between them, and identify metals that could become critical in the upcoming decades. To that end, thermodynamic rarity will be applied for each model analyzed along with the study. Accordingly, the weight of each metal involved in each vehicle has been obtained. Thus, with the values of thermodynamic rarity, obtained from literature review [32] and the weight of each metal it is possible to identify the criticality of a metal in energy terms.

2.2. Models analyzed

In this study, different models of SEAT brands have been considered, taking into account the energy used as a fuel in each of them. The passenger cars analyzed are as follows:

- SEAT Ibiza Generation IV (Diesel and High trimmed)
- SEAT Ibiza Generation IV (Gasoline and High trimmed)
- SEAT León Generation II (Diesel and High trimmed)
- SEAT León Generation II (Gasoline and High trimmed)
- SEAT León Generation III (Diesel and High trimmed)

Table 1. General overview of the cars analyzed.

	SEAT Ibiza Generation IV		SEAT Leon Generation II		SEAT Leon Generation II	PHEV [19]	BEV_333 [19]	BEV_622 [19]	BEV_811 [19]
	Diesel	Gasoline	Diesel	Gasoline	Diesel				
Car weight	1,216.8	1,103.1	1,386.9	1,301.8	1,282.5	1,311	1,745.4	1,738.6	1,730.7
Metal weight	867.3	764.5	996.0	931.0	904.1	1,052.1	1,229.4	1,223.0	1,215.1

Table 1 shows the total weight of each model and the metal content. It must be noted that this difference is due to other components apart from metals, such as plastics and glasses. However, although they have been included in the total weight, they will not be considered in this study. Only ICEV's have been characterized. However, there are similar studies where other technologies have been analyzed, such as plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEV) and BEV [19], [31], [35], which are also summarized in Table 1.

As it is possible to see, there is a big difference between ICEV's and BEVs, not only in car weight but also in the metal component, accounting for almost 400 kg the difference of the weight with the ICEV with fewer metals and the BEV with more weight in metals. Accordingly, Table 2 has been elaborated in order to summarize which are the most metals used when the vehicles analyzed are manufactured. In here, it is appreciated how the main difference in the metal weight is caused by some metals, such as iron, copper and nickel, among others. However, other critical metals are increased their share. For instance, it is spotted that Ag is used between two and three times more in PHEV and BEV than in traditional vehicles (ICEV).

Table 2. Metal composition of each type of vehicle [g].

	SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV. Diesel	SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV Gasoline	SEAT Leon Gen. II Diesel	SEAT Leon Gen. II Gasoline	SEAT Leon Gen. III Diesel	BEV_333 ² [19]	PHEV [19]
Ag	12.27	8.40	16.12	17.92	6.47	34.67	28.00
Al	95,340	88,151	104,307	103,628	90,725	161,464	141,370
As	0.04	0.07	0.37	0.44	0.20	0.88	0.00
Au	2.83	1.45	5.63	6.87	1.05	2.41	0.20
B	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	57.24	0.00
Ba	2,436	2,421	2,225	2,145	927.78	1,634	0.00
Be	0.04	0.31	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.00
Bi	9.83	11.93	10.11	11.36	14.57	34.50	0.00
Cd	0.19	0.23	0.19	0.14	0.24	0.24	0.00
Ce	0.02	48.40	0.69	0.69	0.14	0.14	49.67
Co	31.18	25.59	25.28	21.18	24.48	22,620	2,712
Cr	4,044	3,392	5,422	5,584	6,328	6,534	6,510
Cu	16,664	16,236	18,873	17,276	19,242	59,517	59,166
Dy	1.88	1.74	0.25	1.09	1.10	59.73	13.81
Er	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Eu	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.23
Fe	714,789	622,229	821,806	769,390	744,823	894,671	806,140
Ga	0.41	0.43	0.23	0.23	0.17	0.50	0.81
Gd	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.17
Ge	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.05

² Note that it has been selected only one BEV to simplify the comparison with the vehicles and different technology.

Hf	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Hg	0.26	0.16	0.09	0.00	0.08	0.02	0.00
Ho	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
In	0.30	0.31	0.03	0.03	0.23	0.09	0.38
Ir	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
La	4,79	1.10	0.35	0.35	0.88	3.67	7.38
Li	1.37	0.99	0.96	0.93	4.04	7,955	2,242
Lu	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mg	1,894	2,288	12,424	2,284	11,500	2,339	0.00
Mn	4,280	3,752	4,705	4,537	5,324	27,511	5,968
Mo	297.66	182.24	298.29	211.89	397.61	559.19	260.00
Nb	70.03	78.18	103.36	133.63	222.39	198.23	426.30
Nd	25.91	25.59	28.08	21.44	42.24	972.90	552.79
Ni	1,861	2,412	2,178	3,307	1,877	23,357	16,049
Os	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Pb	10,224	8,733	12,188	11,781	13,062	11,561	9,750
Pd	1.99	1.80	0.85	3.12	3.30	0.42	0.94
Pr	1.62	1.56	0.00	0.65	6.39	9.29	51.48
Pt	0.11	0.08	0.20	0.25	7.37	0.06	5.51
Re	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Rh	0.00	0.09	0.01	0.17	0.24	0.00	0.01
Ru	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.00
Sb	13.24	13.14	21.56	20.87	20.65	129.99	0.00
Sc	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Se	0.05	0.07	0.01	0.03	0.79	0.58	0.00
Sm	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.43	0.00	2.32
Sn	489.53	198.76	329.42	288.71	317.83	392.53	0.00
Sr	205.11	199.38	446.54	381.67	112.29	326.28	0.00
Ta	3.24	2.34	5.04	7.32	6.46	11.51	10.83
Tb	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	2.24	13.62
Te	0.02	0.01	0.36	0.36	0.07	0.04	0.00
Ti	7,751	7,312	2,059	2,136	2,250	1,359	0.00
Th	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tm	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
V	78.74	60.63	115.74	103.37	128.25	146.42	852.61
W	7.65	6.79	9.43	4.78	18.89	5.24	0.00
Y	0.01	0.00	0.06	0.27	0.01	0.10	0.41
Yb	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08
Zn	6,820	6,615	8,444	7,674	6,675	5,921	0.00
Zr	2.07	76.19	2.39	71.00	18.72	6.23	0.00

3. Results

As before mentioned, thermodynamic rarity has been applied to identify not only critical metals but also critical components and car parts of the vehicles characterized in the study. With these criteria, and taking into account only the metals that are manufactured in the vehicles, Table 3 illustrates the different values calculated. What it is shown is the thermodynamic rarity of each vehicle, which has been obtained by multiplying the grams of each metal by its thermodynamic rarity. Then, it is also shown the highest share of a metal depending on the vehicle. In regards to the data obtained, cobalt seems to be the most critical metal since it is the metal that contains the highest thermodynamic rarity from six out of the nine models of vehicles compared. In some models, this share increases up to 85% and 72%. This share in the BEV is due to the amount of cobalt that is needed to produce the batteries since the amount of metal required for this essential element is very high. The other BEV compared "only" holds 52% of a cobalt share. This reduction could be caused because of the improvement and development of new batteries, that in fact, instead of using cobalt, they are being manufactured with more nickel, increasing in more than twice the amount of nickel used in the others BEV [27]. It must be stated that the two main metals with more weight, aluminium and iron, have not been considered for different reasons. First, they can be recycled more easily than the rest of metals, and second, the results would not provide reliable data since the number of metals are orders of magnitude higher in comparison, which have been detected critical by the European Union [37].

Table 3. Thermodynamic rarity comparison depending on the type of vehicle [GJ] and share of the highest metal.

SEAT								
Ibiza	SEAT Ibiza	SEAT Leon	SEAT Leon	SEAT Leon				
Gen. IV.	Gen. IV	Gen. II	Gen. II	Gen. III				
Diesel	Gasoline	Diesel	Gasoline	Diesel	BEV_333	PHEV	BEV_622	BEV_811
108.78	99.02	120.56	125.76	133.89	447.50	214.21	343.51	271.36
Co	Co	Au	Pd	Pt	Co	Co	Co	Co
33.41%	34.00%	19.66%	33.61%	48.73%	85.46%	40.16%	72.40%	52.16%

Although ICEV, PHEV and BEV have been compared through thermodynamic rarity, only different ICEV models have been characterized in this study. As it has been seen, the amount of ICEV for the upcoming years is still very high and therefore, it is necessary to identify which are the most critical components and car parts from ICEV. Once they are identified, it could be possible to establish a procedure to disassembly those car parts to be reused or, as an ultimate procedure, send them to metallurgy processes to recycle to obtain pure metals again.

The identification of critical components has been carried out through the thermodynamic rarity, which has been already explained deeply, and rarity intensity [kJ/g]. It is necessary to introduce this second indicator since it is a ratio between the rarity and the weight of the given component, identifying those components that, despite having little weight, have a high concentration of valuable metals with respect to their total weight. This procedure has already been used by Ortego et al. [38], identifying critical components from a similar study. To that end, as an example (this has been done for the vehicles characterized in the study), Figure 3 shows the classification of the car parts from a vehicle. After this classification, it has been considered critical for those with a thermodynamic rarity higher than 1 G.J. and those belonging to A to G groups, which is medium to high rarity and rarity intensity. It must be noted that car parts with a rarity higher than 1 G.J. are not included in the Figure, although they have been considered critical. This is due to the difference with the rest of the car parts, and they must be analyzed individually.

Figure 3. Car parts distribution according to the Rarity intensity vs Rarity indicators for the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV model. The criticality degree of car parts ranges from A to I in descending order.

According to Figure 3 and for the SEAT Ibiza Gen. IV model as an example, there are 951 car parts in total. Most of them are located on group I and H (low to medium rarity and rarity intensity) being detected 19 in the others, considered critical because of their high value of rarity intensity or their rarity. This means that in this particular case, the 2% of the total car parts represent more than 70% (16.12 GJ) of the total thermodynamic rarity calculated for this vehicle, 22.90 GJ (note that in these values are not included aluminium and iron). This situation is generated for the critical metals that are manufactured in certain car parts, such as gold, platinum, and palladium, among others. In this study, not all the critical parts identified will be analysed but some of them which are common and critical for the different models.

Car parts are manufactured in different ways, depending on the model and the requirements needed in order to carry out its functions properly. The composition of the same car part can be different depending on the

model that is manufactured. Thus, it is possible to find the same car part in different models with different thermodynamic rarity, since the metal requirements change from one model to another. To that end, Figure 4 has been elaborated to identify which car part contains the highest thermodynamic rarity and in which vehicle.

Figure 4. Thermodynamic rarity per car part and model.

To simplify the explanation and the analysis, it has been decided to consider only the Diesel version of the vehicles characterized. Moreover, the main difference with the gasoline version relies mainly on the engine, followed by the generator and starter, remaining the rest of the car parts analyzed the same value as their Diesel version.

The engine has not been included since its rarity is the highest, and its analysis should be carried out individually. This shows how three different car parts are the most critical: infotainment unit, front doors central locking actuator and generator for Leon Gen. III model, Leon Gen. II model and Ibiza Gen. IV, respectively. Accordingly, it must be mentioned that generators contain a similar thermodynamic rarity for the three models and the front lift motor. On the other hand, it highlights the big difference with the front doors central locking actuator for the model Leon Gen. II, being 80 times higher than the other vehicles.

With this, it is possible to identify the most critical car parts from a vehicle from a sustainability point of view. Therefore, once the car parts are identified, it is needed to know why they are critical and which metals are manufactured in that component. Following this line, the next section will analyze the metals involved, spotting the difference in thermodynamic rarity between them.

4. Analysis

This paper aims to identify critical car parts and why they are considered critical. Some components have been selected in the previous section, showing the thermodynamic rarity they composed. However, it is needed to research deeply in order to know why those car parts are unsustainable. Thus, the following analysis will spot the different metals that are critical in the selected components. To develop this process, the sum of the thermodynamic rarity in every metal for each model has been taken into account. Thus, all the metals with a value lower than 1,000 kJ have been not considered critical for the car part that belongs.

4.1. Car parts analyzed

▪ Front doors central locking actuator

There are six metals as critical: silver, gold, copper, nickel, palladium and zinc. Palladium contains the highest thermodynamic rarity with a value two orders of magnitude higher than copper, the second with the highest value. However, palladium is only presented in the Leon Gen. II model. Although gold does not contain a high value, it is similar to palladium, while silver in this model is 125 higher than the other two. On the other hand, there are more nickel and zinc (around four times for each of them) in the Leon Gen. III and Ibiza Gen. IV models than in the Leon Gen. II model.

▪ Front lift motor

In this car part, ten metals have been detected as critical: silver, gold, copper, nickel, palladium, platinum, tin, strontium, tantalum and zinc. Two metals highlight over the rest, gold and tantalum. In regards to the gold, more than 96% is due to the Leon Gen. II model, being 3.5% of the share for the Ibiza Gen. IV model and almost none for Leon Gen. III model. A similar situation happens with tantalum. In this case, there is no Ta in the Leon Gen. III model, being more than 67% of the share for the Leon Gen. II model and around

33% the share for the Ibiza Gen. IV model. It must be named copper for the rest of the metals since its thermodynamic rarity is very high and similar for the three models. Other precious metals, platinum and palladium, are only manufactured in Leon Gen. II and Ibiza Gen. IV models.

- *The onboard supply control unit*

Eleven metals were identified: silver, gold, cobalt, copper, indium, nickel, palladium, platinum, ruthenium, tin and tantalum. Gold and tantalum are the most critical metals in this car part, being the thermodynamic rarity for tantalum twice higher than gold. In this case, the three models hold a similar value, at least in the same order of magnitude for both metals. Palladium is only present in the Leon Gen. III and Ibiza Gen. IV model, while platinum is only in the Leon Gen. II model.

- *Infotainment unit*

This car part is a different case when compared with the rest since there is a model that does not contain this car part. Furthermore, it is the car part where more critical metals have been detected (without taking into account the engine), a total of sixteen metals: silver, gold, cobalt, copper, gallium, indium, manganese, niobium, nickel, palladium, platinum, ruthenium, antimony, tin, tantalum and zinc. In Figure 5 it has been compared the amount of metals contained in two different models. It is noted that the metal with the highest thermodynamic rarity is Ta, followed by Pd in the case of the SEAT Leon Generation II and Au in the case of SEAT Leon Generation III.

Figure 5. Share of each model for the metals identified.

The most critical metal is tantalum, being almost four times higher than palladium, which is the second with the highest value. Gold is in the same order of magnitude as palladium, while the rest of the metals are only remarkable copper, which is one order of magnitude higher than the rest of metals. Figure 5 has been elaborated to see each model's contribution for every metal.

- *Combi-instrument*

There are eleven critical metals identified in this car part: silver, gold, copper, indium, neodymium, nickel, palladium, platinum, tin, tantalum and titanium. The two main metals contain the highest thermodynamic rarity, and their values are similar, gold and tantalum, having the three models the same contribution for each metal. Platinum is also considered one of the most critical in this car part since its value is almost two orders of magnitude higher than the rest of the metals. It must be said that there is no contribution of Leon Gen. III model because it is only manufactured in Leon Gen. II and Ibiza Gen. IV model.

- *Starter*

Ten metals were identified as critical: silver, chromium, copper, manganese, molybdenum, nickel, tin, strontium, tellurium and zinc. There is only one metal that is important to mention in this car part, copper. This metal contains a thermodynamic rarity of more than two orders of magnitude higher than the other metals but tellurium. The only precious metal here is silver, being more than 85% of the contribution for this metal of Leon Gen. III model. In regards to tellurium, 99% of the share is presented in the Leon Gen. III model.

- *Generator*

There are ten metals considered critical in this car part: silver, gold, copper, magnesium, manganese, nickel, palladium, platinum, tin and zinc. The metal with the highest thermodynamic rarity is copper, with a

big difference from the rest of the metals (one order of magnitude higher than gold and three orders of magnitude with the rest of metals). In regards to the precious metal, gold criticality is mainly caused by the Ibiza Gen. IV model, while palladium is present in this vehicle and the Leon Gen. II model.

▪ *Engine*

The engine is the most complex component of a car since it is one of the most important pieces manufactured in a vehicle. As it is possible to see in Figure 6, there are many metals considered critical because of the size of the engine and the number of metals needed to work properly. It must be stated that palladium and platinum for the Leon Gen. III model have not been included in the chart since these values are very high compared with the other metals (twice the amount of palladium in the Ibiza Gen. IV model). Thus, the rest of the metals would not be appreciated if these values were included. It is highlighted that the most critical metal (apart from palladium and platinum) is tantalum, which more than 99% of this criticality is due to the Leon Gen. III model. Other metals are important to mention, like copper and nickel, since their values are similar in the three models and hold a very high thermodynamic rarity for copper and nickel.

Figure 6. Thermodynamic rarity for each metal in in engines in every model analyzed.

4.2. Critical metals identified

As aforementioned, it is not possible to make a fair comparison between the different car parts since different metals and different amounts of them are involved. With the indicator proposed in this study, thermodynamic rarity, it is possible to identify which car parts, therefore, metals, are the most critical. For that reason, Figure 7 has been elaborated to show which metal contains the highest criticality and which car part. Following this criterion, platinum would be the most critical metal, having twice as a thermodynamic rarity as the second with the highest value, palladium (note the logarithmic scale). This is due to the amount of these precious metals involved in the manufacture of the engine of the SEAT Leon Gen. III model.

Figure 7. Sum of the thermodynamic rarity of the three models analyzed.

The next most critical metals are copper, tantalum and gold, which are present mainly in the engine in the case of copper and tantalum, and in the combi-instrument in the case of gold. Figure 7 points out the critical metals detected in this study and those which must be deeply investigated in order to preserve sustainability, not only in the supply chain but also in the vehicles manufactured with these metals.

5. Solutions proposed

There are many industries involved when a car is manufactured since many, and very different car parts must be first produced and then assembled to produce a vehicle. However, at the end of its life, only a few industries aim to recover the main components from the vehicles, and therefore, most of the critical metals are lost when they are shredded. In this line, some solutions are proposed that can be seized not only as a business line but also to become more sustainable in this sector.

- **Change metals.** The viability to return to previous metals applied in this industry can substitute those metals that are scarce on Earth. Some of them can be simply changed by using more non-scarce metal, remaining the same physical and chemical properties that the scarce metal provides to the vehicle.
- **Disassembly.** Another solution could be the disassembly of the vehicle. In this way, it would be possible to use the components disassembled to produce "new models", providing a longer life to the car parts already manufactured, as long as they are in good condition and ready to use.
- **Reparation.** This relies on the mechanics and repairable vehicles. Nowadays, many components in vehicles cannot be repaired because of how they are produced. Then, it is necessary to be able to repair as much as possible, repairing what is broken instead of substituting it, for instance.
- **Consumer culture.** This solution is focused on the society's culture, since most of the time, people prefer new products (car parts and components in this case) rather than second-hand ones. Thus, it is needed to change the mind in order to provide value to reused car parts and understand why they must be assembled again.

6. Conclusions

The car industry has been developing continuously since the first cars were manufactured. The growth of this sector has been exponential, having 1.4 billion passenger cars in the world nowadays. Technology development has provided advances to the automobile sector, not only in driving terms but also in comfort and security terms, among others. Technology development is possible for the use of metals, which provide more efficient and lighter devices.

However, as it has been demonstrated, there are critical metals involved in the car industry and it could be a risk of supply in the following years. For that reason, this study analyzed different models of vehicles, identifying which are the most untenable, comparing which are the car parts with the highest risk index. Three different of ICEVs have been characterized, having the Leon Gen. III model with the highest value of risk index. With the amount of these vehicles expected for the following decades, it is key to identify which are the most critical car parts and metals. Accordingly, it has been found that infotainment, front doors, central locking actuator and generator are the most unsustainable car part for Leon Gen. III model, Leon Gen. II model and Ibiza Gen. IV model respectively. In the case of metals, it has been spotted that there is a possibility of risk of supply for copper, platinum, palladium, tantalum and gold. Therefore, it is crucial to carry out research to find solutions to avoid a bottleneck that could put the automobile sector at risk.

Large amount of metals are going to be needed in the following years to be able to produce cars. Thus, it is necessary to find new sources of extraction or find the way to manufacture more sustainable vehicles. To that end, some solutions have been proposed, such as changing metals, a deep reparation in broken car parts, disassembling, etc. Nevertheless, many changes must be carried out in the sector, and authorities must support them. Fostering new practices, law regulations and new recycling measures (among others) have to be promoted to raise awareness of this situation through society.

On the other hand, it has been shown that engine is the most critical car part from a vehicle. This is explained because of the weight of it, since it is the most important component of a vehicle. New car generations are expected to play a key role in the following years, increasing the share of BEV and PHEV in the fleet. These engines could require more critical metals and make less sustainable the manufacture of a vehicle, so it is essential to research how reduce the metal impact in this sector.

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